

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17173171

Urban Tree Leaf Wastes in Soil amendment: Effects on Soil Hydrothermal Properties, Nematode Infestation and Tomato Growth

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to evaluate the effect of urban tree leaf mulches and manures on soil properties, root-knot-nematodes and growth of tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill). The results indicated significant increase ($P < 0.05$) in mean soil moisture content of the leaf litter mulches over the control during the growth period of tomato was observed. *Citrus sinensis* recorded the highest soil moisture content of 4.9%. Soil temperature was significantly decreased ($P < 0.05$) by the leaf litter mulches relative to the control. *Azadirachta indica* leaf mulch showed the least soil temperature of 28.30C while *Magnifera indica* indicated the highest temperature of 29.20C. Vegetative growth parameters of tomato were significantly increased by nutrient applications. Organomineral applications of 25% NPK +75% MI gave the highest effect on the plant height, leaf number, leaf area, leaf area index, number of branches and biomass yield. Plants treated with nutrient applications had significant effect ($P > 0.05$) on yield components and yield of tomato. Tomato plants that received mulching materials of *Azadirachta indica* (22.8) and *Citrus sinensis* (25.8) showed the greatest reduction in number of galls on tomato roots with values of 43.4% and 36% respectively over the control. The study recommended the use of *Azadirachta indica* and *Citrus sinensis* urban tree leaves for optimum reduction of nematode infestation in tomato infested soils. Farmers can also achieve optimum growth and yield of tomato from use of composted urban tree leaves or organominerals (mixture of NPK and composted urban tree leaves).

Keywords: urban tree leaf mulches, root-knot-nematodes, *Azadirachta indica*, *Citrus sinensis*

INTRODUCTION

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) belongs to the family of Solanaceae and is one of the most popular and nutritious vegetable crop. As it is a relatively short duration crop and gives a high yield, it is economically attractive and the area under cultivation is increasing daily. In Nigeria, tomato yields output when compared with the average yield of 13.5 t ha⁻¹ for other tropical Africa and the world average of 22 t ha⁻¹. In the meantime, the shortage in the months of peak rainfall (May – November) and a production glut in the months of harvesting (March to May and September to October) lead to dichotomy in the distribution of annual tomato production across all agroecological zones.

The yield of tomato is greatly limited by unfavourable soil microclimate, poor soil nutrient status and pests/diseases (Tswanya et al., 2017). Agrochemicals have been used in improving soil environment to

enhance tomato yield, but the high costs and adverse environmental effects hamper their continuous usage.

Low soil fertility could threaten the security of food production and supply. Soil fertility is a major overriding constraint that affects all aspects of crop production. In the past years, inorganic fertilizer was advocated for crop production to ameliorate low inherent fertility of soils in the tropics. In addition to being expensive and scarce, the use of inorganic fertilizer has not been helpful in intensive agriculture because it is often associated with reduced crop yield, soil acidity and nutrient imbalance (Agbede *et al.*, 2008). The need to use renewable forms of energy and reduce costs of fertilizing crops has revived the use of organic fertilizers worldwide (Ayoola and Adeniyani, 2006). Large quantities of organic wastes such as poultry manure are available especially in urban centers and are an effective source of nutrients for vegetables such as tomato (Adediran *et al.*, 2003).

Leaf wastes shed from urban trees can also serve as soil amendment for mulching and nutrient application. Conventional practice in urban areas is collection of the leaf wastes, disposal into bins where they are later burnt in open fires. The need for alternative uses to urban leaf wastes that are sustainable and environmentally friendly becomes very significant.

The main objective of the study is to evaluate the effect of urban tree leaf wastes on soil hydrothermal properties, nematode infestation and tomato growth

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Three field experiments were conducted.

Experiment 1: The field experiment was a randomized complete block design consisting of eight (8) treatments replicated thrice. The eight (8) treatments were made up of dried leaves of seven (7) trees; (*Magnifera indica*, *Anacardium occidentale*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Terminalia mentalis*, *Citrus spp.*, *Gmelina arborea*, *Tectona grandis*) and unmulched or control. Leaf litter fall from trees planted within the Delta State University, Abraka and its environs were collected for use as organic mulch. Three (3) weeks old tomato seedlings were transplanted into plots of 3m x 3m and planted 60 cm x 30 cm. Dried leaves were applied at the rate of 10 t/ha *ex-situ*.

Table 1. Common names, scientific names and family of urban tree leaves used for the study

Scientific name	Common name	Family
<i>Magnifera indica</i>	Mango	Anacardiaceae
<i>Anacardium occidentale</i>	Cashew	Anacardiaceae
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Neem	Meliaceae
<i>Terminalia mentalis</i>	Umbrella tree	Combretaceae
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Orange	Rutaceae
<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Gmelina	Lamiaceae
<i>Tectona grandis</i>	Teak	Lamiaceae

Measurement of Hydrothermal Properties

Measurements of soil temperature were collected bi-weekly at a depth of 10 cm at 8:00 am and 4:00 pm with the aid of mercury soil thermometer. From each experimental plot, the soil moisture content was taken using tension meter at the soil top 10 cm layer.

Using the methods described by Tian *et al.* (1994) duration effect of moisture / temperature of the soil were estimated from the time period within which the moisture/temperature of the soil is more than the average LSD_{0.05} over the experimental period, while the prime effect is the mean decrease in the soil temperature/moisture compared to the control within the first 30 days after mulch application.

Experiment 2: The experiment was made up of eight (8) treatments consisting of dried leaves of seven (7) trees; (*Magnifera indica*, *Anacardium occidentale*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Terminalia mentalis*, *Citrus spp*, *Gmelina arborea*, *Tectona grandis*) and unmulched or control. Dried leaf litter was applied *in situ* at a depth of 10 cm and at rate of 10 t/ha. After washing the roots, *Meloidogyne* damage was assessed by visual examination and counting of number of galls.

Experiment 3: Dried and milled leaf litter of *Magnifera indica* and *Anacardium occidentale* were mixed with cow manure at a ratio of 5:1 and allowed to compost for 30 days. To prevent loss of materials and contamination with other materials, the closed container composting method was used. The experiment was a randomized complete block design consisting of six treatments and replicated thrice. The six treatments were as follows:

F1- Control

F2- NPK-15-15-15 (300kg ha⁻¹)

F3- Composted *Magnifera indica* (10 t ha⁻¹)

F4- Composted *Anacardium occidentale* (10 t ha⁻¹)

F5-25% (75 kg ha⁻¹) NPK-15-15-15 + 75% (7.5 t ha⁻¹) Composted *Magnifera indica*

F6-25% (75 kg ha⁻¹) NPK-15-15-15 + 75% (7.5 t ha⁻¹) Composted *Anacardium occidentale*

Crop parameters collected were plant height, number of leaves, leaf area, days to 50 % of flowering, number of flower, and number of fruits per plant, dry weight, fresh weight and total fruit yield. The Leaf-Area Index (LAI) was calculated by dividing the total leaf area (LA) of the plant by the total land area (La). Biomass yield of tomato plants were obtained by cutting the vegetative parts 5cm above the ground level to obtain the fresh shoot weight. Dry weight was determined through oven drying of plant samples per plot at 65 °C for 48hours at 10 WAT.

Soil parameters: The soil samples collected were air-dried and analysed for particle size: sand, silt and clay (Bouyoucos hydrometer method), pH (in water), organic matter (Walkley Black), total nitrogen (Kjeldahl), available phosphorus (Bray 1), and exchangeable K, Ca, Na, Mg (ammonium acetate).

Data were presented as average of two cropping seasons. All data were analysed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) as described by Gomez and Gomez (1984). Means were separated using the least significant difference (LSD) at 5% level of probability

RESULTS

Table 2: Prime effects and mean soil moisture content and temperature of leaf litter mulch during the period of growth of tomato

Treatments	Soil moisture content (%)		Soil temperature (°C)	
	Means	Prime effect	Means	Prime effect
Control	2.2		29.7	
<i>Magnifera indica</i>	3.5	1.2	29.2	-0.5
<i>Anacardium occidentale</i>	3.7	1.4	28.3	-1.4
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	4.1	1.8	28.8	-0.9
<i>Terminalia mentalis</i>	3.2	0.9	27.8	-1.9
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	4.9	2.5	28.4	-1.3
<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	4.7	2.3	28.6	-1.1
<i>Tectona grandis</i>	4.6	2.3	28.7	-1.0
LSD (5%)	0.6		0.9	

Table 3: Duration effects (in days) of soil moisture content and temperature of leaf litter mulch during the period of growth of tomato

Leaf litter mulch	Duration effects (in days)	
	Soil moisture content (days)	Soil temperature (days)
<i>Magnifera indica</i>	44	43
<i>Anacardium occidentale</i>	45	51
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	33	32
<i>Terminalia mentalis</i>	36	37
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	43	42
<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	33	38
<i>Tectona grandis</i>	38	36

Significant increase ($P < 0.05$) in mean soil moisture content of the leaf litter mulches over the control during the growth period of tomato was observed (Table 2). Amongst the leaf litter mulch from urban agroforestry trees, *Citrus sinensis* recorded the highest soil moisture content of 4.9% while *Terminalia mentalis* indicated the least value of 3.2%. The order of mean soil moisture content of leaf litter mulches was *Citrus sinensis* > *Gmelina arborea* > *Tectona grandis* > *Azadirachta indica* > *Anacardium occidentale* > *Magnifera indica*. Prime effect of soil moisture content was at its maximum value (2.5) in tomato plots mulched with *Citrus sinensis* leaf litter while *Terminalia mentalis* (0.9) recorded the least. *Anacardium occidentale* leaves mulch showed a longer soil moisture duration effect (45 days) while *Azadirachta indica* and *Gmelina arborea* leaves equally indicated the shortest duration effect of 33 days on the soil (Table 3).

Soil temperature was significantly decreased ($P < 0.05$) by the leaf litter mulches relative to the control (Table 2). Amongst the tree leaf mulches, *Azadirachta indica* leaf mulch showed the least soil temperature of 28.3°C while *Magnifera indica* indicated the highest temperature of 29.2°C. The order of soil temperature of leaf litter mulches was *Magnifera indica* > *Azadirachta indica* > *Tectona grandis* > *Gmelina arborea* > *Citrus sinensis* > *Anacardium occidentale* > *Terminalia mentalis*. The prime effect of soil temperature was at its maximum in *Magnifera indica* (-0.5) and the lowest value in *Terminalia mentalis* (-1.9). The longest duration effect of soil temperature was exhibited in *Anacardium occidentale* leaf (51 days) mulched plots while the least was observed in *Azadirachta indica* (32 days) (Table 3).

Table 4. Effect of Composted Urban Tree Leaf Wastes Manure on Soil Chemical Properties

Treatments	pH _{H2O}		OC (%)		N (%)	
	PC-1	PC-2	PC-1	PC-2	PC-1	PC-2
Control	6.2	6.2	0.91	0.97	0.76	0.84
NPK-15-15-15	6.2	6.4	0.91	1.23	0.76	1.25
Composted MI	6.2	6.7	0.91	1.95	0.76	1.43
Composted AO	6.2	6.7	0.91	1.96	0.76	1.42
25% NPK +75% MI	6.2	6.5	0.91	1.87	0.76	1.40
25% NPK +75% AO	6.2	6.5	0.91	1.88	0.76	1.45
LSD (5%)		ns		0.05		0.07

PC-1: pre-cropping PC-2: post cropping

The result of the soil chemical parameters as shown in Table 4.4 indicated that the treatments applied had effect on the chemical parameters of the soil. Except pH which showed non-significance, organic carbon and nitrogen were significantly affected by applied nutrients. Soils of tomato plots applied with composted AO and 25% NPK +75% AO recorded the highest organic carbon (1.96) and nitrogen (1.45) respectively.

Effect of Composted Urban Tree Leaf Wastes Manure on Growth And Yield Of Tomato

Table 5: Plant height (cm) of tomato as influenced by composted urban tree leaf litter and NPK

Treatments	Weeks after transplanting (WAT)				
	2	4	6	8	10
Control	13.6	22.4	32.8	49.5	62.3
NPK-15-15-15	14.9	25.0	34.2	53.6	65.2
Composted MI	14.8	24.9	35.6	55.5	66.7
Composted AO	14.7	24.8	36.0	56.1	68.2
25% NPK +75% MI	15.3	25.9	36.3	57.9	68.8
25% NPK +75% AO	15.8	25.6	36.8	58.2	68.5
LSD (5%)		ns			

MI-*Magnifera indica*; AO-*Anacardium occidentale*

Results in Table 5 indicated that tomato plants showed no significant difference between nutrient applications ($P>0.05$) within the first 2 WAT. However from 4 WAT, nutrient applications consistently resulted in significant increase ($P>0.05$) in plant height. Tallest tomato plants at 10 WAP were obtained from plots that received 25% NPK +75% MI (68.8cm).

Table 6: Number of leaves of tomato as influenced by composted urban tree leaf litter and NPK

Treatments	Weeks after transplanting (WAT)				
	2	4	6	8	10
Control	19.6	38.7	70.5	98.6	140.6
NPK-15-15-15	21.3	40.6	72.8	105.7	158.3
Composted MI	21.9	41.3	74.6	110.8	162.8
Composted AO	22.4	42.5	75.3	115.1	164.2
25% NPK +75% MI	22.0	41.8	76.8	116.7	170.5
25% NPK +75% AO	21.6	42.6	77.1	116.6	173.8
LSD (5%)	ns				

MI-*Magnifera indica*; AO-*Anacardium occidentale*

The effect of nutrient applications on number of leaves of tomato indicated significant difference ($P>0.05$) at 4 WAT (Table 6). Highest number of leaves were obtained from tomato plants that received 25% NPK +75% MI (170.5cm) and 25% NPK +75% AO (173.8 cm).

Table 7: Biomass of tomato as influenced by composted urban tree leaf litter and NPK

Treatments	Shoot weight (g plant ⁻¹)	Root weight (g plant ⁻¹)	Shoot: root ratio
Control	125.3	40.6	3.1
NPK-15-15-15	131.8	43.8	3.0
Composted MI	136.8	42.9	3.2
Composted AO	141.9	43.2	3.3
25% NPK +75% MI	148.2	43.8	3.4
25% NPK +75% AO	158.8	43.8	3.6
LSD (5%)	3.6	0.13	ns

MI-*Magnifera indica*; AO-*Anacardium occidentale*

As presented in Table 7, with exception of Shoot: root ratio, which Roma VF treated with 25% NPK +75% AO significantly ($P>0.05$) performed better with biomass attributes such as shoot weight (158.8 g plant⁻¹) and root weight (43.8 g plant⁻¹). All the nutrient applications outperformed the control by 5.2% (NPK), 9.2% (composted MI), 13.2% (composted AO), 18.3% (25% NPK +75% MI) and 26.8% (25% NPK +75% AO).

Table 8: Components of yield and fruit yield of tomato as influenced by composted urban tree leaf litter and NPK

Treatments	No. of flowers (plant ⁻¹)	No. of fruits (plant ⁻¹)	Flower to Fruit ratio	Mean fruit weight (g fruit ⁻¹)	Fruit yield (kgha ⁻¹)
Control	16.3	12.7	1.28	23.9	14.8
NPK-15-15-15	18.7	14.9	1.25	28.3	16.3
Composted MI	19.3	15.3	1.26	29.3	18.1
Composted AO	19.7	15.6	1.26	28.9	17.7
25% NPK +75% MI	20.7	16.9	1.22	29.8	19.8
25% NPK +75% AO	21.3	18.3	1.16	30.7	20.8
LSD (5%)	0.41	0.46	0.15	0.23	0.34

MI-*Magnifera indica*; AO-*Anacardium occidentale*

Plots treated with nutrient applications had significant effect ($P>0.05$) on yield components and yield of tomato as shown in Table 8. Relative to the control, NPK application significantly increased number of flowers by 14.7%, while composted *Magnifera indica* and *Anacardium occidentale* resulted in 18.4% and 20.9% increase respectively. However the best results were achieved with the organo-mineral applications from 25% NPK +75% MI and 25% NPK +75% AO which attained 27% and 30.7% increase respectively over the control.

The results which were supported by statistical analysis showed that all three classes of nutrient applications (mineral, organic and organo-mineral) significantly ($P>0.05$) increased the number of fruits per tomato plant. Application of 25% NPK + 75% AO organo-mineral showed the greatest increase of 44.1%, while NPK had the least effect (17.3%).

Similarly, the increase in fruit weight of tomato plants showed the greatest effect in plants treated with 25% NPK +75% AO with an increase of 28.5%, and 24.7% with composted AO, while lower increased value of 18.9% were observed with plants which received only NPK.

Similarly, the increase in tomato fruit yield relative to the control attributed to nutrient application of NPK (mineral fertilizer) was 10.1%, while composted MI and AO ranged from 19.6% to 22.3% and the organo-minerals ranged from 33.8% to 42.9% in plots with application of 25% NPK +75% MI and 25% NPK +75%.

Table 9: Number of nematode galls per tomato plant root as influenced by urban tree leaf litter

Treatments	No. of galls Per 10g root
Control	40.3
<i>Magnifera indica</i>	35.2
<i>Anacardium occidentale</i>	33.5
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	22.8
<i>Terminalia mentalis</i>	30.5
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	25.8
<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	30,5
<i>Tectona grandis</i>	31.7
LSD (5%)	

The results presented in Table 9 which were supported by statistical analysis indicated that all seven organic materials significantly decreased the level of harmful nematodes as shown by reduced number of galls. Tomato plants that received mulching materials of *Azadirachta indica* and *Citrus sinensis* showed the greatest reduction in number of galls on tomato roots with values of 43.4% and 36% respectively over the control.

DISCUSSION

The magnitude of desired effect depends on quality and durability of mulch. Application of leaf litter mulches in this study resulted in enhanced soil moisture content which would have been due to decrease in moisture evaporation from the soil. Mulch has a great role in modification of soil hydrothermal regimes. The water holding capacity of the soil improved through mulch degradation and humus formation (Ji and Unger, 2001). This conserved moisture and balanced soil temperature is important for nutrient transporting, translocation of assimilate, cell division, and cell differentiation (Teame *et al.* 2017). The findings are in consonance with earlier observations of Mkhabela *et al.*(2019) which reported significant difference in soil moisture retention for grass mulch and control showing that organic mulch reduces evaporation of soil moisture and thus improving soil moisture retention (Hernandez *et al.*, 2016) Urban tree leaf mulches which resulted in favourable soil hydrothermal properties consequently enhanced tomato parameters such as plant height, umber of fruits/plant, fruit weight and fruit yield observed, shoot biomass. This could be attributed to hydrothermal sensitivity of physiological processes (production of

leaves, increase in plant height and attainment of anthesis). These results are in consonance with the observations of Pressman *et al.*, (2002) and Agele *et al.* (2006). It can also be attributed to the more favourable environmental conditions from the applied mulch influencing growth and development of tomato (Oladitan and Oluwasemire, 2018).

The findings of these study and that of other researchers confirm that the increase in nematode population and subsequent reduction in yield of crops or other manifestations of pathogenic effects, morphological responses are directly influenced by initial density of nematodes in soil (Mukhtar *et al.*, 2013; . This study agrees with previous reports of Liman *et al.* (2010) that indicated the use of plant materials in the nematode control and further observed reduced nematode population on tomato seedlings treated with leaf extract from the mahogany plant than on untreated tomato seedlings. In a related study, Estelle *et al.* (2025) reported that neem and castor extracts induced a low rate of multiplication of t nematodes in the same way as furasol, and reduced the number of nematodes in the soil and roots of treated tomato plants.

Organic manures, such as composts promotes early and vigorous growth of seedlings effectively enhancing root formation, elongation of stem and biomass production in plants (Ahemad and Kilbet 2020). On the whole, the growth performance of the tomato crop as exemplified by plant height, leaf number, dry weight was good determinant to yield throughout the study period. In this study application of organomineral manures as soil amendment had more pronounced effect on growth and yield attributes of tomato plants compared to mineral fertilizers alone. The higher response of tomato to the growth might be due to the availability of essential elements, increased organic matter, nitrogen, and possibly other nutrients released from the incorporated organomineral fertilizers. The positive effects of plant based organic mulches in enhancing yield components and yield of tomato has been reported in other studies Tswana *et al.* 2017).

Crop growth, yield and product quality in relation to application of compost or in combination with small doses of mineral fertilizer has been widely reported (Ilupeju *et al.*, 2015). High fruit yield of plants nourished with organic fertilizer could be due to the fact that the materials not only contained sufficient nutrients but the nutrients are slowly released to the plants. This prevents nutrient loss and leaching, as well as improving nutrient use efficiency. All these facilitate higher production of economic part of the plant. It could be observed that the higher the compost contents of some treatments, the better the plant performance in terms of fruit yield and quality. Many research works have reported higher nutritional values of organically grown vegetables when compared with inorganic ones. This could explain the better yield and yield components of tomato plants nourished with pure compost (Composted MI or Composted AO) or that containing high amount of compost (NPK + Composted MI and NPK + Composted AO). Compost contained many active sites which improved soil cation exchange capacity (CEC) and fertility. This stimulates better nutrient uptake and utilization by the crop. In the present study, combined application of compost with NPK improved the efficiency of the former.

Related studies conducted by Allahyari *et al.* (2014) had shown the potentiality of organic manures such as vermicomposts in improving growth and yield of different field crops due to the presence of macro and micro nutrients. Demir and Kiran (2020) and Mahmud *et al.* (2020) confirmed the capacity of vermicomposts in supplying macro and micro nutrients essential for optimum plant growth on lettuce.

The higher yield components for tomatoes grown on soils amended with bio-enriched vermicomposts corroborates the work of Antoniou *et al.* (2017) who reported better rooting and plant growth due to the application of vermicomposts. Research conducted by many workers had reported the efficacy of vermicomposts on the growth, productivity and quality of various crop plants (Moraditochae *et al.*, 2011).

Azadirachta indica and *Citrus sinensis* leaves were recommended as good mulching materials for maintaining suitable soil temperature and moisture content for tomato growth. Mulching with The study recommended the use of *Azadirachta indica* and *Citrus sinensis* urban tree leaves for optimum reduction of nematode infestation in tomato infested soils. Farmers can also achieve optimum growth and yield of tomato from use of composted urban tree leaves or organominerals (mixture of NPK and composted urban tree leaves).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Our sincere appreciation to the Tertiary Education Trust Fund for providing the funds for the research through the Institution Based Research (IBR) to Delta State University, Abraka with Reference number TETF/DR&D/CE/UNI/ABRAKA/IBR/2021/VOL 1

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